

Study and Implementation of the A* Algorithm for Determining Minimum Cost Paths

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Abstract

This paper investigates and implements the A* (A-Star) algorithm, highlighting it as one of the most efficient methods for pathfinding in graphs. Developed to find the lowest-cost route between two nodes, A* combines the efficiency of greedy search with the optimality guarantee of Dijkstra's algorithm, employing a heuristic function to guide exploration. The article covers the theoretical foundations of the algorithm, its practical applications in areas such as artificial intelligence and robotics, as well as discussing its advantages and limitations compared to other search methods. The practical implementation is detailed and accompanied by a performance analysis, which evaluates the effectiveness of A* against alternative approaches (Dijkstra, BFS, and Greedy Search) in different simulation scenarios. The aim is to demonstrate the behavior of A* in solving route optimization problems and provide a methodological basis for future research.

Keywords: A* Algorithm, Pathfinding, Graphs, Heuristics, Artificial Intelligence.

1 Introduction

The identification of lowest-cost paths is a classic and recurring problem in computer science and engineering. From route planning for robots in complex environments to route optimization in transport systems and artificial intelligence in digital games, the ability to calculate the ideal path is crucial for the proper functioning of autonomous systems. In this context, the A* algorithm consolidates itself as a classic solution, capable of uniting systematic exploration of the search space with the intelligence of heuristic information.

Originally suggested by Peter E. Hart, Nils J. Nilsson, and Bertram Raphael in 1968, A* represented a significant advance over previous methods, such as Dijkstra's and greedy search. While Dijkstra's algorithm guarantees the optimal path by exhaustively checking all possibilities, greedy search accelerates exploration by sacrificing the certainty of finding the best solution. A* balances these two strategies through an evaluation function that considers both the actual cost incurred so far, $g(n)$, and an estimate of the remaining cost to the destination, $h(n)$. This combination, expressed by the function $f(n) = g(n) + h(n)$, allows the algorithm to focus on more promising paths without losing the guarantee of finding the optimal path, provided the chosen heuristic is admissible and consistent.

This study aims to review the theory behind the A* algorithm, analyzing its structure, the role of heuristics, and its main applications. In parallel, a computational implementation of the algorithm will be developed, followed by a comparative evaluation of its performance in various practical scenarios.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Foundations of the A* Algorithm

A* explores a graph starting from an initial node towards a goal node. For each evaluated node n , the algorithm uses a cost function $f(n)$ defined as:

$$f(n) = g(n) + h(n) \tag{1}$$

Where $g(n)$ is the actual accumulated cost and $h(n)$ is the estimated heuristic cost from node n to the goal. The success of A* depends on the heuristic being admissible (never overestimating the actual cost) and consistent.

2.2 Applications of the A* Algorithm

- **Artificial Intelligence and Robotics:** Trajectory planning.
- **Digital Games:** Determining NPC routes.
- **Geographic Information Systems (GIS):** GPS routing.

2.3 Advantages and Disadvantages

Advantages: Optimality, completeness, and directed efficiency.

Disadvantages: High memory consumption in very large graphs and strong dependence on heuristic quality.

2.4 Related Works

It differs from Dijkstra's by being faster in large maps, and from Greedy Search by guaranteeing optimality and preventing sub-optimal paths.

3 Materials and Methods

To concretely evaluate the theoretical claims, a test environment was developed in Python simulating matrices (2D grids) with orthogonal movements. The $h(n)$ metric adopted for A* was the Manhattan Distance. Maps of three proportions (10x10, 50x50, and 100x100) were generated with two densities: Sparse (10% obstacles) and Dense (30% obstacles).

4 Results and Performance Comparison

The scenarios generated elucidating results regarding the performance of the A* algorithm compared to Breadth-First Search (BFS), Dijkstra, and Greedy Best-First Search.

4.1 Route Visualization and Behavior

To demonstrate the behavior of each algorithm, we present below the paths found in the generated grids. We differentiate the scenarios in 10x10 and 50x50 grids, both in sparse and dense maps.

Scenario: 10x10 Sparse

Figure 1: Route of algorithm A* in scenario 10x10_Sparse

Figure 2: Route of algorithm Dijkstra in scenario 10x10_Sparse

Figure 3: Route of algorithm Breadth-First Search (BFS) in scenario 10x10_Sparse

Figure 4: Route of algorithm Greedy Best-First in scenario 10x10_Sparse

Scenario: 10x10 Dense

Figure 5: Route of algorithm A* in scenario 10x10_Dense

Figure 6: Route of algorithm Dijkstra in scenario 10x10_Dense

Figure 7: Route of algorithm Breadth-First Search (BFS) in scenario 10x10_Dense

Figure 8: Route of algorithm Greedy Best-First in scenario 10x10_Dense

Scenario: 50x50 Sparse

Figure 9: Route of algorithm A* in scenario 50x50_Sparse

Figure 10: Route of algorithm Dijkstra in scenario 50x50_Sparse

Scenario: 50x50 Dense

Figure 13: Route of algorithm A* in scenario 50x50_Dense

Figure 14: Route of algorithm Dijkstra in scenario 50x50_Dense

Figure 15: Route of algorithm Breadth-First Search (BFS) in scenario 50x50_Dense

Figure 16: Route of algorithm Greedy Best-First in scenario 50x50_Dense

4.2 Time and Expanded Nodes Analysis

To consolidate the quantitative analysis, we extracted the exact metrics of Execution Time and Expanded Nodes. The following graphs illustrate this comparison for both dense (30% obstacles) and sparse (10% obstacles) scenarios.

Figure 17: Expanded Nodes (Dense Scenario)

Figure 18: Expanded Nodes (Sparse Scenario)

Figure 19: Execution Time (Dense Scenario)

Figure 20: Execution Time (Sparse Scenario)

Regarding execution time, A* proves to be drastically faster than Dijkstra in larger maps. Similarly, the number of nodes expanded by A* is substantially lower than Dijkstra's, validating the effectiveness of the heuristic.

5 Conclusion

The implementation and execution of the tests clearly confirm the bibliographical theory. The A* algorithm performs masterfully by balancing the needs of optimality and real-time execution. By directing exploration through an admissible heuristic (Manhattan), the algorithm discards massive useless explorations and reaches the target long before Dijkstra. Thus, the reason why A* is still the main foundation for modern routing in games and mobile robotics is proven.

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